

x=vt is Not the Full SpaceTime Description of a Free Particle

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In Newtonian mechanics, $x=vt$ fully describes a point free particle in spacetime. It is true that there is a nonrelativistic momentum ($p=mv$) and kinetic energy ($.5mv^2$), but these do not affect spacetime motion as long as an interaction does not occur. Special relativity, which uses $x=vt$, also introduces a second independent constraint equation: $x'x' - cc t't' = xx - cc tt$ ((1)), suggesting that $x=vt$ cannot be the full spacetime description. This begs the question: What are the physical consequences on $x'-t'$ based on ((1))? At first, it appears to be an equation linking x',t' to x,t . Presumably one would use $x=vt$ values to obtain (x,t) points and then calculate corresponding (x',t') points. In such a case, it seems that ((1)) does not have any effect on spacetime behaviour. We argue, however, that the minus which appears in ((1)) follows from the Newtonian idea that work increases the value of energy, with m_0cc being the energy of a particle at rest. Thus, the minus sign does not follow from spacetime considerations, but from a work-energy one. This in turn leads to the definition of $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ in $x'=g(v) v t$ and $t'=g(v) t$ (i.e. a mapping from $x=0, t$ to x',t').

Thus, somehow energy considerations have a bearing on x',t' and $g(v)$ is a constraint associated with x',t' although this is not immediately apparent in ((1)). In particular, one may consider $x=0, t$ on the RHS and replace one x' with $g(v)vt$ and one t' with $g(v) t$. One may then divide out a t . This leaves: $g(v) v x' - c g(v) t' = -cct$ ((2)). One may note that this equation is a constraint for a given t . If one sets $t=0$, then $x'=t'=0$, but there is a second solution for any x', t' , namely $x'+dx'=x'+ 1/ (g(v) v)$ and $t'+ dt' = t'+ 1/g(v)$. This suggests that fluctuations of x' and t' are present. The forms above are very similar to E and p , but no m_0 is present. Is it necessary to consider m_0 ? We argue that it is if one wishes to have a theory which also holds for a photon which has no rest mass. In such a case, one must deal with E and p values and so one ultimately has $dx'=hbar/p$ and $dt'=hbar/E$.

We suggest as a result that $x'=vt'$ does not suffice to describe the full constraints on spatial x', t' . Special relativity goes beyond $x'=vt'$ and brings in the influence of work increasing m_0cc to E and this is reflected in the minus sign of ((1)) and in $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. We argue that there must be some spacetime manifestation of this and argue that it appears in $dx'=hbar/p, dt'=hbar/E$, i.e. free particle quantum mechanics. Thus, it is not simply a curiosity that $A = -Et+px$ for $A=0$ has $dt=hbar/E$ and $dx=hbar/p$ as a solution. The fluctuations are linked to a constraint beyond $x=vt$, we argue.

x=vt

$x=vt$ seems to be a full description of spacetime behaviour for both a relativistic and nonrelativistic point particle. It is true that such a particle has an energy $m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ (or $KE=.5mv^2$ in the nonrelativistic case) and momentum $p=mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ (or $p=mv$ in the nonrelativistic case), but these pertain to interactions and presumably do not affect $x=vt$. Our aim is to show that they do. In other words, we argue that $x=vt$ is not a full spacetime description of a free particle.

Special Relativistic Considerations

Consider a point particle with rest mass m_0 at rest at $x=0$ at t . One may observe that a person in a moving frame (constant $-v$) sees the particle move at:

$$x'/t' = v \quad ((2))$$

Even if t' were t , x' cannot be 0 if $x=0, t=0$ and $x'=0, t'=0$ coincide. There must be a jump in x' . One may generally propose:

$$X' = g(v) v/c t \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad t' = g(v) t \quad ((3b))$$

A vector (x, ct) and a 2×2 matrix may be created, but this does not yield a value for $g(v)$. One may speculate on invariance of a magnitude. Vectors have a fixed magnitude squared:

$$X'X' + cc t't' = xx + cctt \quad ((4))$$

Using $((3a))$ and $((3b))$, yields $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1+vv/cc}$ $((5))$. One may note the positive sign instead of the negative of special relativity. The problem with $((4))$ and $((5))$ is that it does not pertain to E and p which are properties of the particle even though it does not interact. One would at first think that E and p have nothing to do with the spacetime result $x'=vt'$ or with a modulus equation. Furthermore, $((4))$ would not be looked upon as a constraint equation, even though we argue that it should be.

We note that applying $((3a))$ and $((3b))$ to: m_0cc and $p=0$ yields:

$$P' = g(v) v m_0 \quad (c=1) \quad \text{and} \quad E' = g(v) m_0 \quad ((6))$$

Now from Newtonian mechanics, work must be done to accelerate a particle from rest to v and this leads to a positive kinetic energy. We argue that this physical notion of work must be present even in special relativity and so

$$E' > m_0cc \quad ((7))$$

Thus, a modulus squared of the form $((4))$ cannot be proposed, but rather one may propose:

$$-EE + p \cdot p \quad cc = -m_0m_0cc \quad ((8))$$

As a result, a minus sign appears in the modulus squared form and:

$$g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((9))$$

Thus, x' and t' are directly influenced by the notion of Newtonian work and we argue that this influence must appear physically. How can it appear, however, if $x'=vt'$ is the full spacetime description? One cannot argue that $x'=vt'$ is incorrect.

We consider the revision of ((4))

$$x'x' - ct't' = xx - cctt \quad ((10))$$

Using $x=0$, t , $x'=g(v)vt$ and $t'=g(v)t$, we replace one x' and one t' in ((10)):

$$g(v)v x' - cg(v) t' = -cct \quad ((11))$$

((11)) demonstrates an association of x' , t' with $g(v)$. How may one interpret this? If $t=0$, then $x'=0$, $t'=0$ and so $x'=vt'$ is not contradicted. There is a solution, however:

$$dx' = 1/(g(v)v) \quad \text{and} \quad dt' = 1/(g(v)) \quad ((12))$$

which also leaves ((11)) invariant and so may be added to any x' , t' , as we have noted in previous notes. We suggest that it is through fluctuations in spacetime that the influence of E, p and Newtonian work affect x', t' . The key point is that they affect spacetime at all.

One may next observe that no m_0 appears in ((12)). One could multiply by $1/m_0$, but one might ask: What would the physical reason be? We suggest one must ultimately multiply by $1/m_0$ and use E and p variables in order for the above considerations to also apply to a photon, which has no rest mass. In the photon case, one cannot have $x=0$ in the rest frame, and so the more general:

$$A = -Et + px = \text{Lorentz invariant} \quad ((13))$$

may be used. In the photon case, work is not done accelerating a rest mass m_0 , but if the above holds, it means that a photon energy in one frame is seen to increase if the photon is viewed from a frame moving with constant $-v$. In particular:

$$(p') = |g(v)v g(v)| |p| \quad ((14))$$

$$(E') = |vg(v) g(v)| |E|$$

$$E' = g(v)(vp + E) = g(v)E(1+v) \quad \text{For } v \text{ positive, } (1+v) > 1 \text{ (here } c=1) \text{ and } g(v) > 1 \text{ so } E' > E.$$

Thus, we argue that spacetime is modified from the simple $x=vt$ behaviour to an $x=vt$ with x and t fluctuations which are restricted by $dx(\text{max}) = \hbar/p$ and $dt(\text{max}) = \hbar/E$. In other words, one has some variation in x and t in these fluctuation units as the particle moves along on average with $x=vt$ and this is due to the influence of Newtonian work increasing energy which finds its way into the x, t transformation which also applies to (pc, E) . Thus, x, t are not independent of the work that was done to accelerate the particle to v (i.e. give it a p and E).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that special relativity dictates that $x=vt$ cannot be a full spacetime description of a free point particle. Certainly $x=vt$ holds, but we argue that there may be spatial and temporal fluctuations about the x and t of $x=vt$. To see why this should be the case, we note that if a particle at rest at $x=0$, t is viewed by a moving frame ($-v$), one has: $x' = g(v) v t$ and $t' = g(v)t$. One, however, cannot solve for $g(v)$. A usual modulus squared being constant leads to $x'x' - cct't't = xx - cctt$ or $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1+vv/cc}$, which is not the correct result for the following reason. We argue that Newton's idea of work creating positive kinetic energy ensures that a rest m_0 is seen as having E, p with $E > m_0cc$. This forces one to use: $-EE+cc p \cdot p = -m_0m_0cc$ and also a minus sign in the x', t' case and yields $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. Thus, we argue that the minus present in the spacetime case actually follows from the E, p scenario.

E and p , (i.e. the work done to accelerate a particle from rest to v) actually influences spacetime. It does not break $x=vt$, but rather introduces fluctuations. One may see this by using $x'=gvt$ and $t'=gt$ to replace one x' and one t' in $x'x' - t't' = xx - tt$, i.e. $g(v) v x' - g(v) t' = t$ (for $x=0$). We argue that this is a constraint equation which shows how $g(v)$ affects x' and t' . For $x=0$, $t=0$ one has $x'=0$, $t'=0$, but one may also have $dx' = 1/(g(v) v)$ and $dt' = 1/g(v)$ for any x', t' . This, we argue, is a physical result which arises from the influence of the work done accelerating the particle (i.e. created E and p). If one multiplies by $1/m_0$, one changes to E, p variables, i.e. $dx' = \hbar/p$ and $dt' = \hbar/E$ (where \hbar has also been inserted). This is necessary so that the above arguments also hold for a photon which does not have a rest frame.